
CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND FIRM PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The unresolved puzzle as regards the relationship between capital structure and firms' performance actually engendered this study to specifically ascertain how certain components of capital structure influence performance of quoted companies conceptually. In the methodology section, the study employs the desk top review approach to carefully assess existing literatures.

Findings made reveal that capital structure has significant impact on the performance of firms. The effects are both positive and negative. It spells out that the result is still very inconclusive. Premised on this, it is suggested that firms should on the basis of financing needs adopt an appropriate mix of debt and equity that should enhance its performance and shareholders wealth.

Keywords: long term debt, short term debt, equity, optimal financing mix, firm performance.

Introduction

A lot of studies have actually been done by numerous researchers both in developed and developing countries such as Nigeria to ascertain the empirical relationship existing between capital structure and firm performance with varying samples and period as well as application of several and divergent statistical estimation. Different capital structure variables such as short term debt, long term debt, total debts and equity have been analyzed against performance measures vis-à-vis Return on Asset (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Profit before interest and tax (PIBT), profit after tax (PAT) and earnings per share (EPS), just but to list a few. One major thing that could be deduced from this myriad of studies on capital structure relationship with firm performance is that no one has clearly and finally established the exact impact of capital structure on firm performance and to what extent should firms apply capital structure in their financing decision?

The capital structure of a firm may be seen as the combination of debt and equity that make up the sources of corporate assets (Ahmadpar & Yahyasadehfar, 2010). However, the size and magnitude of capital structure differ markedly from one firm to the other. Decision taking as regard capital structure and how it affects the corporate performance is highly sensitive and critical to a financial manager. This is because inappropriate mix of the capital structure would have an 'effect' on the firm earnings and on the overall shareholders.

Review of Related Literature

Meaning of Capital Structure

Capital structure has to do with the relationship of debt to equity a firm employs in financing its operation with a view to achieving the set goals and objectives. Firm financial goals encompass profit maximization as well as shareholders wealth maximization. According to Damodaran (2001), capital structure decision is the mix of debt and equity that a company uses to finance its business. The capital structure of a firm is a mix of debt and equity that is used by a firm to enhance its operation (Zuraidah, Norhasuiza & Shashazrina, 2012). In this view, capital structure decisions therefore represent another important financial decision of a business organ section apart from investment decisions.

Capital structure in a simple term involves a firm employing huge amount of cash in form of debt and on equity to finance its operation, and it has both short-run and long-run implications on that firm. There has to be a strategy the firm uses to organize the appropriate mix of the debt and equity although no theory has been established to specify the exactness of the debt or equity a firm should use to finance its operation and at what specific period and situation. This in real sense in terms one of the reasons studies as regard capital structure on firm performance has been on for decades and is expected to extend to decades of years to come.

Osuji and Odita (2012), state that capital structure is the means by which an organization is financed; and it is the mix of debt and equity capital maintained by a firm. They shared the view that how an organization is financed is of paramount importance to both the managers of the firms and providers of fund. They note that if a wrong mix of finance is employed, the performance and survival of the business enterprise may be seriously affected. Patrick, Joseph and Kemi (2013) aver that a firm's capital structure refers to the mix of its financial liabilities. This definition of capital structure above is quite revealing. First, they see debt and equity as the two major classes of liabilities, with debt holders and equity holders representing the two types of investors in the firm.

Each of these investors investment is associated with debt varying level of benefits, risk and controls. For instance, the debt holders exert lower control on the management and utilization of the debt capital in a firm; and they only earn a fixed a determined rate of return (fixed interest charges) and by law are protected with contractual obligations as regards their investments (i.e. debt capital they invest into a given firm). Similarly, the stock (equity) holders appear to be the residual owners. They bear the highest risk and however possess a greater control of decision making in terms of the assets of the firm.

Furthermore, capital structure according to Hasan, Ahsan, Rahaman and Alam (2014), is the combination of a firm's long term debt, specific short term debt, common equity, preferred equity and retained earnings which are used to finance its overall operations and growth. The term capital structure is defined by Weston and Brigham (1979) as the permanent financing of the firm represented by long term debt, preferred stock and net worth. Van Home and Wachowicz (1995) state that capital structure is the mix of a firm's permanent long term financing, represented by debt, preferred stock and common stock equity.

Ong and The (2015), see capital structure to refer to the firm's financial framework which consists of the debt and equity used to finance the firm. Capital structure in financial term means the way a firm finances their assets through the combination of equity, debt or hybrid securities (Saad, 2010). Subsequently, Ong and The (2015) point out that capital structure is essential on how a firm finances its overall operations and growth by using different sources of funds. Taiwo (2012) defines capital structure as the means by which an organization is financed; it is also a company's proportion of short and long term debt and is considered when analyzing capital structure. He also sees capital structure as the mix of debt and equity maintained by a firm. Amara and Bilal (2014) see capital structure to be the blend of internal and external sources of funds used by the firms to finance their assets. Capital structure is about putting in place the structure, processes and mechanism that ensure that the firm is being directed and managed in a way that enhances long term shareholder value through accountability of managers and enhancing organizational performance (Kajananthan & Nimalthasar, 2013).

From the above numerical definitions of capital structure, it can be observed outrightly that capital structure of a firm is somewhat difficult to determine. In other words, there is actually no real optimal capital structure a firm can maintain to enhance its value. Up till date, there is no formula or theory that was decisively provides optimal capital structure for a firm, hence the need to continually evaluates how it directly or indirectly influences the operations and performance of a firm from time to time.

Theoretical Framework

Trade-off Theory

The trade-off theory refers to the idea that a company chooses how much debt finance and how much equity finance to use by balancing the costs and benefits. Trade-off theory allows the bankruptcy cost to exist. It states that there is an advantage to financing with debt (namely, the tax benefit) and that there is a cost of financing with debt (the bankruptcy costs and the financial distress costs of debt). The marginal benefit of further increases in debt declines as debt increases, while the marginal cost increases, so that a firm that is optimizing its overall value will focus on this trade-off when choosing how much debt and equity to use for financing. Empirically, this theory may explain differences in D/E ratios between industries, but it doesn't explain differences within the same industry.

Pecking Order Theory

In the theory of firm's capital structure and financing decisions, the pecking order was first suggested by Donaldson in 1961 and it was modified by Myers and Majluf. It states that companies prioritize their sources of financing (from internal financing to equity) according to the principle of least effort, or of least resistance, preferring to raise equity as a financing means of last resort. Hence, internal funds are used first, and when that is depleted, debt is issued, and when it is not sensible to issue any more debt, equity is issued. Pecking Order theory tries to capture the costs of asymmetric information. It states that companies prioritize their sources of financing (from internal financing to equity) according to the law of least effort, or of least resistance, preferring to raise equity as a financing means "of last resort". Hence: internal financing is used first when that is depleted, then debt is issued and when it is no longer sensible to issue any more debt, equity is issued. This theory maintains that businesses adhere to a hierarchy of financing sources and prefer internal financing when available, and debt is preferred over equity if external financing is required (equity would mean issuing shares which meant 'bringing external ownership' into the company). Thus, the form of debt a firm chooses can act as a signal of its need for external finance. The pecking order theory is popularized by Myers, when he argues that equity is a less preferred means to raise capital because when managers (who are assumed to know better about true condition of the firm than investors) issue new equity, investors believe that managers think that the firm is overvalued and managers are taking advantage of this over-valuation. As a result, investors will place a lower value to the new equity issuance.

Agency Theory

This is a theory concerning the relationship between the principal (shareholders) and the agent of the principal (company's managers). This suggests that the firm can be viewed as a nexus of contracts (loosely defined) between resource holders. An agency relationship arises whenever one or more individual, called principals, hire one or more other individuals, called agents, to perform some service and then delegate decision-making authority to the agents.

Empirical Relationship between Capital Structure and Firm Performance

A lot of empirical studies have been done to explore if there is any positive, negative or no relationship between firms' performance and capital structure in both developed and developing countries of the world; most of the results have rather produced mixed results.

Pathak (2011) in his study find out that the level of debt has significant negative association with firm performance. Kester (1986) found a negative relationship between capital structure and performance (profitability) in the US and Japan. Similar results were reported by Friend and Lang (1988), Titman and Wessels (1988), from the US firms, Rajan and Zingales (1995) in the G-7 countries, Wald (1999), Haung and Song (2006) too ascertain a negative correlation between leverage and performance (Earnings before interest and tax to total assets of China firms. Ebaid (2009) find a weak-to-no impact of capital structure on firm performance.

Champion (1999) suggests that the use of leverage is one way to improve the performance of the firm. Mesquita and Lara (2003) find long term debt is not significantly related to ROE and it has negative sign, showing potential inverse relationship. Gilason, Mathur, and Mathur (2000) had examined the relationship between performance and leverage by using return on asset. The result indicates that total debt has a significant negative influence on performance.

Ebrati, Emadi, Balasong and Safari (2013) explore the relationship between capital structure and firm performance on the non-financial listed companies of Tehran stock exchange for the period 2006-2011. The empirical results indicate that capital structure is negatively related with EPS and ROA as performance measures.

Onaolapo and Kajola (2010) investigate the effect of capital structure on financial performance of companies listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange. The study was performed on 30 non-financial companies in 15 industry sectors in a 7-year period from 2001 to 2007. The result shows that capital structure was a significant negative effect on financial measures such as ROA and ROE of these companies.

Roden and Lewellen (1995) examined the relationship between capital structure and profitability of firms and ascertained a positive relationship between profitability and capital structure in U.S. Hadlock and James (2002) in their view suggest corporations with high level of profitability use high level of debts. Abor (2005) reports a positive relationship between capital structure and performance of firms over the period 1998 – 2002 in Ghanaian firms. Arbiyan and Safari (2009) investigate the impact of capital structure on profitability of Iranian listed firm from 2001 to 2007 and found short term and total debts are positively related to profitability using return on equity (ROE).

Sa'eed, Gull and Rasheed (2013) studied the impact of capital structure on performance of listed banks of Karachi Stock Exchange in Pakistan for the period of 2007-2011. The result capital structure had strong positive relationship with the firms' performance. Tianyu (2013) examined the influence of capital structure on firms' performance. The result indicates significant positive effect.

Gleason, Lynette and Ike (2000) concluded that high levels of debt in the capital structure would reduce the firm's performance. They observed that firm's capital structure has a statistically significant negative effect on firm's performance matrixes, i.e. return on assets (ROA), growth in sales (Gsales), and pretax income (Ptax).

A negative link between capital structure and firm's performance was also witnessed by Fama and French (2002). They observed that highly profitable firms with lower risk of financial distress are actually less levered which contradicts with the trade-off theory.

Nor and Fatihah (2012) tried to explore the impact of debt and equity financing on the performance of the firms listed in Bursa Malaysia. Using a sample of 130 firms for the period 2001-2010 combined with multiple regression analysis, they cited a statistical significant negative relation between capital structure and firms' performance.

Using a sample of 237 Malaysian companies during 1995-2011, Salim and Yadav (2012) studied the relationship between capital structure and firm performance. Their analysis revealed that firm performance measured by ROAD, ROE and EPS have negative relationship with the capital structure while Tobin's Q has significantly positive relationship with STD and LTD. Similar result was observed by Zeitun and Tian (2007) in their study for a sample of 167 Jordanian companies during 1989-2003.

Ali and Iman (2011) observed that firm's performance, calculated by EPS and Tobin's Q, is positively related with the capital structure, while they got a negative relation between capital structure and ROA. However, they witnessed no significant relationship between ROE and capital structure. Same result was also found by Ebrati, Farzad, Reza, and Ghorban (2013).

Abor (2005) also investigated the link between capitals structure and profitability of firms listed in Ghana Stock Exchange for the period 1998-2002. Using regression analysis, he witnessed a significantly positive relation among ROE and the short-term debt and total debt ratio, while, a negative relation with long-term debt.

Ibrahim (2009) also examined the influence of capital-structure choice on firm performance in Egypt. His study based on a sample of non-financial listed firms for the period 1997 to 2005 and used multiple regression analysis. Results suggested that firm performance has weak to no relationship with capital structure choice. Likewise, Khalaf (2013) also found negative and insignificant relationship between short-term and long-term debt ratio, and ROAD and profit margin.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has conceptually evaluates the relationship between capital structure and firm performance. Evaluation of existing literature has revealed capital structure effect on firm performance still remain inconclusive. There is no optimal capital structure decision a firm can actually employ to influence in performance. Premised on this, it is suggested that firms should on the basis of financing needs adopt an appropriate mix of debt and equity that should enhance its performance and shareholders wealth.

References

- Patrick, O., Joseph, O. & Kemi, A. (2013). The impact of capital structure on firm's performance in Nigeria. Munich Personal RepEc Archive Paper No. 46173.
- Ong, T.S. & The, B.H. (2015). Capital structure and corporate performance of Malaysian construction sector. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(2): 26-31.
- Osuji, C.C. & Odita, A. (2012). Impact of capital structure on the financial performance of Nigerian firms. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(2): 43-52.
- Ahmadpour, A. & Yahyazadehfar (2010). Financial management, leverage (7thed.). Mazardaran University, No. 1.
- Taiwo, A.M. (2012). An empirical analysis of capital structure on firms' performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 6(2): 116-128.
- Kajanankan, R. & Nimalthasan, P. (2013). Capital structure and its impact on firm performance: A study on Sri Lankan listed manufacturing companies. *Merit Research Journals*, 1(2): 37-44.
- Hasan, B., Ahsan, A.F.M., Rahaman, A. & Alam, N. (2014). Influence of capital structure on firm performance: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(5), 184-189.
- Champion, D. (1999). 'Finance the joy of leverage', *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 77, No. 4: p. 19-22.
- Damodaran, A. (2001). *Corporate Finance: Theory and Practice*, (2nded.). Wiley.
- Ebaid, I.E. (2009). 'The impact of capital-structure choice on Firm Performance: Empirical Evidence from Egypt', *The Journal of Risk Finance*, Vol. 1Q, No. 5, pp. 477-487.
- Gleason, K.C., Mathur, L.K. and Mathur I. (2000). 'The interrelationship between cultures, capital structure, and performance: Evidence from European retailers'. *Journals of Business Research*, Vol. 50, pp. 185-91.
- Ebrati, M.R., Emadi, F., Balasang, R.S., & Safari, G. (2013). The impact of capital structure on Firm/Performance: Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Science*, 7(4):1-8.
- Khan, A.G. (2012). The relationship of capital structure decisions with firm performance: A study of the engineering sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting* 21(1): 245-262.

Saeed, M.M., Gull, A.A. & Rasheed, M.Y. (2013). Impact of capital structure on banking performance (A case study of Pakistan). *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(10): 393-403.